

EFFECTIVE TEACHING METHODS IN THE CLASSROOM

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Annotation: This article describes the content of professional-pedagogical competence of future teachers, forms and methods of its improvement, qualities of professional competence and their essence. In improving the professional competence of the future specialist, the stages of work on oneself, forms of self-evaluation through self-development, analysis and monitoring are given. The necessity of developing innovative special programs for improving professional and pedagogical competence, proposals and recommendations on its components were developed, conclusions were presented.

Key words: pedagogy, psychology, competence, profession, innovation.

In the world education system, many researches and projects on the development of education are being carried out, especially the development of all components of pedagogical professional training is of great importance. In our country, in order to improve the mechanisms for the development of pedagogical professional competences, a modern material and technical base has been created in educational institutions, and innovative educational programs have been developed.

In 2017-2021, the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the task of "raising a highly educated and intellectually developed generation based on the achievements in the educational system of developed countries, creating a reserve of competent scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions" [1].

At the same time, in many reforms carried out in our country, in the process of developing a civil society based on democratic principles, the need to further improve the professional competencies of pedagogues was emphasized in the higher education system. In the conditions of market relations, resistance to strong competition, which takes priority in the labor market, shows the need for each specialist to have professional competence, to increase it consistently. In the implementation of these tasks, it is necessary to create effective innovative models based on the principles of multi-level coherence, continuity and consistency in the context of education, to develop the professional competencies of pedagogues.

In connection with the development of globalization and international integration, the expansion of socio-economic relations, there is a need for mechanisms that allow rapid exchange of information on professional competences, and these issues determine the relevance of this topic.

In higher educational institutions in the field of pedagogy, it is important to increase the intellectual potential of future teachers, to enrich their worldview, to introduce them to innovative educational technologies, new, innovative forms, methods and tools of teaching, to familiarize them with the qualities of professional competence and creative ability of pedagogues.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Among the scientists of our republic, L. Akhmedova, U. Begimkulov, N. Muslimov, B. Rahimov, N. Taylokov, Sh. Sharipov and others have conducted scientific researches on social-pedagogical, acmeological issues in the field of education, and in these researches, the issues of improving the professional competences of specialists in certain areas directly cited. Also,

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pedagogic scientists H. Abdukarimov, N. Azizkho'jaeva, A. Aliev, Yu. A. Akhrorov, A. A. Verbitsky, R. H. Joraev, B. R. Joraeva, J. G'. Yoldoshev, S. M. Markova, G. M. Makhmutova, A. A. Hamidov, F. R. Yuzlikaev have also been researched.

In the scientific studies of scientists such as V. Baydenko, A. Zalevskaya, E. Zeer, I. Zimnyaya, O. Polyakov in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, the issues of analysis and systematization of methods of formation and improvement of professional competences in various processes were considered.

However, the lack of development of the integrative content and methodical conditions for the development of professional and pedagogical competence of officers-teachers of higher military educational institutions based on innovative approaches requires conducting scientific research in this direction.

RESULTS

Modernizing the educational process in higher education institutions, developing the professional competence of future teachers in improving the quality level of the system of training pedagogues, equipping them with modern professional knowledge, qualifications and skills related to the field, creative use of scientific and technical innovations, and the ability to solve prospective tasks independently. development of skills is one of the important tasks. Modernization of the higher education system (visually modern - updated, modern, rapid growth) requires an innovative approach to the educational process. V. A. Slastenin explains the innovative approach to the pedagogical process by introducing innovations in the purpose, content and form of the organization of cooperative activities of teachers and students [2].

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. In the State Educational Standard of General Secondary Education, approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 187 dated April 6, 2017, the concept of competence is defined as the ability to apply existing knowledge, skills and abilities in daily activities [3]. From a psychological point of view, competence means "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of conflicts, has a plan of movement in consistently developing and complex processes." Based on the above considerations, it can be concluded that competence is a person's ability to solve a certain problem based on existing knowledge and life experiences.

One of the important components in the implementation of innovations in the educational process in higher education institutions is the professional competence and innovative activity of the teacher. In relation to the concept of professional competence, various attitudes are advanced in the scientific field. It is used as a feature that describes specific activity requirements for the labor subject, or precisely, the subject's attitude to specific aspects of specific activities. For example, the research scientist E. F. Zeer's study of the functional development of professional competence shows that various forms of competence become integrated during professional maturity and their relationship with professional important personal qualities becomes stronger [4]. In particular, the main levels of professional competence include professional training and experience, self-awareness, confidence in one's own strength, correct acceptance of shortcomings shown by other people, and other such personal characteristics that determine professional maturity. The analysis of the above-mentioned points allows the professional competence of the pedagogue to be fully explained as a set of specific characteristics such as personal, social, creative, methodical competence [5].

Professional competence refers to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level. There are different definitions and approaches to this concept. According to N. M. Muslimov,

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"competence" (incl. "competence" - "ability") means the effective use of theoretical knowledge in activities, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional qualifications, skill and talent [6].

According to V.I.Andreev, competence is a developing integrated indicator that manifests itself in solving certain educational, professional and other complex issues, and it is a level of preparation of a person that includes positive motivation, knowledge, skill, talent and experience of creative activity [7].

N.V. Tarasova interprets the concept of competence as a general ability based on knowledge, values and perception, which allows to ensure connection between knowledge and situation, knowledge and action aimed at solving a problem [8].

DISCUSSION

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work. Professional competence is evident in complex processes, performing ambiguous tasks, using conflicting information, being able to have a plan of action in an unexpected situation, and other similar situations.

Professional-pedagogical competence refers to specialists who have perfectly developed their professional skills, can effectively design and manage the teaching process, and can successfully apply educational reforms, modern requirements, and innovative paradigms in the teaching process.

Therefore, the future teacher will achieve professional competence by consistently enriching his professional-pedagogical knowledge, assimilating new information, searching for new knowledge with a deep understanding of the requirements of the time, processing them and effectively applying them in his practical work. It should be mentioned that there are a number of qualities based on pedagogical professional competence, the essence of which can be explained as follows.

1. Social competence - the ability to show activity in social relations, the ability to engage in communicative dialogue with subjects in professional-pedagogical activities.

2. Special competence is preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activities, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic evaluation of activity results, consistent development of BKM, based on this competence, spiritual (psychological), methodological, informational (informational), creative (non-standard), innovative and communicative competence is noticeable. They represent the following content:

- psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, to be able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in time;

- methodological competence - methodically rational organization of the pedagogical process, the ability to correctly define the forms of educational or educational activities, to choose methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, to use them effectively;

- informational competence - searching for, collecting, sorting, processing necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment and using them quickly, purposefully and effectively;

- creative competence - a critical and creative approach to pedagogical activity, the ability to demonstrate one's creativity skills, the ability to find comprehensive and diverse solutions to problems;

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- innovative competence - putting forward new ideas on improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and successfully implementing them into practice;

- communicative competence - to communicate sincerely with all participants of the educational process, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive influence on them.

- personal competence - consistently achieving professional growth, increasing the level of competence, demonstrating one's internal capabilities in professional activity;

- technological competence - mastering advanced technologies that enrich professional-pedagogical BKM, being able to use modern tools, techniques and technologies;

Individual development programs of a professional-pedagogical nature developed by a future teacher should include the following components along with pedagogical, psychological and specialist knowledge:

- didactic skills (knowledge-related (gnostic) design, creative-practical (constructive), research, accessibility to communication (communicative), organization, ensuring consistency (procedural), technical-technological skills);

- skills for organizing educational work (knowledge-related (gnostic) design skills, creative-practical (constructive) research, accessibility to communication (communicative), organization ensuring consistency (procedural) technical-technological skills);

- professionally important characteristics of the psyche and personal qualities (pedagogical thinking, systematicity, flexibility, mobility, creativity, responsiveness, emotional development, pedagogical reflection);

- self-development goals and related tasks, etc.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that in the individual development programs aimed at improving the professional-pedagogical competence of the future teacher, it is recommended that the current level of pedagogical knowledge, skills and personal qualities and prospective tasks aimed at the development of this competence are mentioned. This, in turn, is a product of effective activity in constantly monitoring the dynamics of professional development of future teachers at various levels, as a result of which the parts of competence that should be paid attention to the professional competence of a pedagogue are clearly visible, and this gives an impetus to its development. In educational processes conducted by a teacher with high professional-pedagogical competence, the process of covering each subject and topic will help the students to become high-potential and competitive personnel in the future. First of all, it serves as the main factor for the development of society

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Жамиятда барқарор ривожланиш ва ижтимоий адолатни таъминлашда gender tengligi муҳим омиллардан бири ҳисобланади¹. Таълим жараёнида шахснинг дунёқараши, ижтимоий фаоллиги ва касбий йўналиши шаклланади, шу боис gender tengligi масаласи педагогикада муҳим аҳамият касб этади².

Халқаро ташкилотлар (БМТ, ЮНЕСКО, ЮНИСЕФ) таълимда gender tengligini таъминлашга қаратилган концепциялар ва стратегиялар ишлаб чиққан³. Ўзбекистон Республикасида ҳам сўнгги йилларда gender tengligi давлат сиёсати даражасига кўтарилди⁴. Бироқ амалиёт шунини кўрсатадики, таълим жараёнида ҳали ҳам gender stereotiplari сақланиб қолмоқда⁵.

Шу нуқтаи назардан, таълим jarayonida gender tengligini ta'minlashning педагогик асосларини тадқиқ этиш ва самарали педагогик механизмларни ишлаб чиқиш долзарб вазифа ҳисобланади.

1. Gender tengligining назарий асослари

Gender tengligi — ўқувчиларга жинсидан қатъи назар тенг таълим, ривожланиш ва ижтимоий фаоллик имкониятлари яратишни англатади⁶. Педагогик назарияда бу тушунча шахсга йўналтирилган таълим, инклюзив таълим ва ижтимоий-педагогик ёндашувлар билан узвий боғлиқдир⁷.

ЮНЕСКОнинг “gender-responsive pedagogy” концепцияси таълим jarayonida барча ўқувчилар учун тенг муҳит, дискриминацияга йўл қўймастик ва pedagoglarning gender kompetentligini ривожлантиришни назарда тутуди⁸.

2. Pedagogik шарт-шароитлар

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Ta'lim jarayonida gender tengligini ta'minlash kуйидаги педагогик шарт-шароитларга боғлиқ:

- O'qituvchilarning gender kompetentligini rivojlantirish⁹;
- O'quv dasturlari va darsliklarda gender yondashuvni ta'minlash¹⁰;
- Ta'lim muhitida tenglikka asoslangan psixologik iqlim yaratish¹¹.

Педагогнинг genderga oid bilim va qarashlari o'quvchilarning faolligi va o'quv natijalariga bevosita ta'sir kўrsatadi. Шу bois pedagog kadrlarni tayyorlashda gender masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratish zarur.

3. Xalqaro tajriba va milliy amaliyot

Xalqaro tajriba kўrsatadiki, Finlandiya va Kanada ta'lim jarayonida genderga sezgir yondashuvlar joriy qilingani ta'lim sifatini va ijtimoiy barqarorlikni oshirgan¹².

Ўзбекистонда esa gender tengligi masalalari ta'lim siyosatiga bosqichma-bosqich integratsiya qilingani. Bu maqsadda normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar qabul qilinmoqda va pedagoglar uchun maxsus treninglar tashkil etilmoqda¹³.

4. Pedagogik mexanizmlar va tavsiflar

Ta'lim jarayonida gender tengligini ta'minlashda kуйидаги mexanizmlar samarali hisoblanadi:

- Dars jarayonlarida barча o'quvchilarning teng ishtirokini ta'minlash;
- Interfaol va hamkorlikka asoslangan metodlardan foydalaniш;
- O'quvchilarda gender stereotiplarini kamaytirishga qaratilgan tarbiyaviy mashg'ulotlar;
- Pedagoglar uchun gender treninglari va seminarlar¹⁴.

Хулоса

Ta'lim jarayonida gender tengligini ta'minlash — pedagogik, ijtimoiy va huquqiy ahamiyatga ega kompleks jaraen. Genderga sezgir pedagogika asosida tashkil etilgan ta'lim o'quvchilarning шахсий va ijtimoiy rivojlaniшига хизмат қилади. Шу bois, халқаро тажрибани миллий амалиёт билан уйғунлаштириб, ta'lim jarayonida gender tengligini ta'minlash mexanizmlarini izchil rivojlantirish zarur.

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